

Synthesis of N-Isobutyl Trans-4, Trans-6-Decadienamide

BALDEV VIG and SATVIR DEHIYA

Department of Chemistry, K. U. Regional Centre for Post Graduate
Studies, Rohtak (Haryana)

and

G. L. KAD and BHAGAT RAM

Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14.

Manuscript received 8 April 1974; revised 19 November 1974; accepted 19 November, 1974

The reaction of γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate with butaldehyde yielded ethyl trans-2, trans-4 octadienoate (I). LiAlH_4 reduction of (I) affords the corresponding allylic carbinol (II) which was converted to corresponding bromide with phosphorous tribromide. Alkylation of bromide (III) with diethyl malonate followed by refluxing with sodium cyanide in dimethyl sulphoxide afforded compound (V). The compound (V) on hydrolysis gives acid (VI), which on treatment with thionyl chloride and condensation of the resulting acid chloride with isobutylamine gives the desired product (VII).

VARIOUS types of acid amides have been isolated from plant sources and these compounds have been shown to be important for their physiological and insecticidal behaviour¹⁻³. Gerber⁴ was first to isolate spilanthol, an alkyl acid amide from *S. oleracea* Jacq. The same material was obtained by Asano and Kanematsu⁵ and again by Gokhale and Bhide⁶ from flower heads of *S. acmella* L. On the basis of its chemical reactions and degradation studies Spilanthol has been assigned N-isobutyl-4,6-decadien amide structure (Geometrical configuration unknown). N-isobutyl Trans-4, Trans-6-decadienamide has been synthesised and found to be a powerful sialogog with insecticidal activity⁷.

The present communication describes a new synthesis of the title compound. The major step designated in the synthetic approach is modified Wittig reaction of an appropriately substituted aldehyde with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate for the creation of two trans double bonds in conjugation in the molecule.

N-Butaldehyde was submitted to modified Wittig reaction with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate in presence of sodium hydride using tetrahydrofuran as solvent. Phosphonate of ethyl crotonate was prepared from triethyl phosphite and ethyl γ -bromo crotonate by Michael Arbuzov reaction. This resulted in the formation of ethyl trans-2, trans-4-octadienoate (I) in 60% yield. As reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁰ the modified Wittig reaction with electron acceptor group at the ylid carbon of phosphorylide molecule tends to be stereospecific and yields only trans isomer. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$ 1705, 1655, 1620, 995 cm^{-1} . (consistent with the presence of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$

of the ester grouping and to avoid hydrogenation of the conjugated double bonds $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{film}}$, 3360, 1650, 1625, 990 cm^{-1} .

grouping). The conjugated ester (I) was reduced with LiAlH_4 in benzene to bring about hydrogenation

The allylic carbinol (II) was converted into corresponding bromide (III) by reacting with phosphorus

tribomide in ether in dark which on subsequent alkylation with ethyl-malonate furnished diethyl trans-2, trans-4-octadienyl malonate (IV). The compound (IV) was then refluxed with sodium cyanide in dimethyl-sulphoxide¹¹ for four hours to provide ethyl trans-4, trans-6-decadienoate (V) in 57% yield. ν_{max}^{film} 1735, 1640, 1615, 990 cm^{-1} (consistent with saturated ester and trans conjugated double bonds). Hydrolysis of ester (V) with 15% alcoholic KOH gave trans-4, trans-6-decadienoic acid (VI) in 70% yield ν_{max}^{film} 3400-3050, 1705, 995 cm^{-1} (carboxyl and trans double bonds). The acid (VI) was converted into corresponding acid chloride with thionyl chloride in benzene as solvent. Benzene and excess thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was then condensed with isobutylamine in ether to furnish N-isobutyl trans-4, trans-6-decadienamide in 65% yield (VII). Purity of the compound (VII) was checked by TLC and it was characterised through IR and UV spectroscopy, ν_{max}^{film} 3350 (NH), 1655 (-C-NH-), 1620, 1600 and 990 cm^{-1}

(trans double bonds). λ 231 nm.

References

1. P. B. SONNET, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **84**, 1147.
2. S. D. PRICE and A. R. PINDER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1970, **35**, 2568.
3. J. SINGH, C. K. DHAR and C. K. ATAL, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1971, 2119.
4. E. GERBER, *Arch. Pharm*, 1903, **241**, 270.
5. M. ASANO and T. KANEMATSU, *J. Phara. Soc. Japan*. 1927, **47**, 521.
6. V. G. GOKHLE and B. V. BHIDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **22**, 250.
7. M. Jacobson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5084.
8. L. D. BERGELSON and M. M. SHEMYAKIN, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 149.
9. D. H. WADSWORTH, D. E. SCHUPP, E. D. SEUS and A. J. FORD, *J. Org. Chem.* 1965, **30**, 680.
10. P. J. VAN-DEN TAMPLE and D. H. HUISMAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 293.
11. A. P. KRAPCHO, G. A. GLYNN and B. O. GRENON, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 215.